

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING DIDACTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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Abstract. *The process of professional retraining allows you to develop the skills and competencies of employees using basic tools. The volume of knowledge, scientific information and skills of trainees, their attitude towards solving complex problems and wider organizational issues can create an environment of mutual understanding between employees and organizations, create conditions for solving problems and strengthening a sense of cooperation. All this leads to a significant increase in efficiency.*

Keywords: *professional retraining, students, advanced training, personal development, teacher, professional activity.*

The basis of a person's professional development is the multifaceted nature of his activities, culture, moral position, and professional skills. Some literature notes that "development" is realized through "formation", while another emphasizes that "becoming" is realized through "development"[11].

According to L.I. Ansiferova[12], "personal development is associated with the teacher's ability to be the subject of his own development, and personal development is not something that happens "for this person," the personality constantly seeks and builds types of relationships to the limits of the world in which unique the potentials of a particular person can be best demonstrated and developed" [12].

In our opinion, the use of a set of methods of social influence in various types of activities that have professional significance for a person includes professional development.

From the point of view of N. David, the improvement of human resources is defined in a certain sense as the training of employees in order to increase the potential of employees and prepare specialists for current tasks [16].

Training forms are aimed at helping employees develop competencies and skills and help improve productivity. From a practical point of view, employee training is used in relation to the opportunity to improve the training method in the future.

The importance of highly trained education personnel is to avoid duplication in the work of staff and their support. Education and training, as well as management tools, are inseparable parts of each other.

Teacher retraining is a type of systematic work on professional training, the main goal of which is the coordination and harmonization of the aspirations, interests and needs of students, taking into account future requirements and goals.

From the above, we can conclude that the education system is determined by teachers working in this field, relying on various methods, including textbooks, courses, long-term and short-term courses.

The best educational methods for teacher retraining are based on practical results. In order to enhance the educational potential and experience of employees through training courses, enrich

the content requirements for the quality of training courses, regular and continuous development and all-round growth in the future, various meetings and study groups, visits, ruzes (lectures), as well as improving educational activities are held mandatory.

High-quality conduct of educational activities, the use of information and communication technologies, advanced and innovative forms and methods of training and education established by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, Requirements for taking into account psychological and unique features of the physical and mental health and physiological development of students are identified[1].

It should be said that the training plan includes the development of employees and the ability to solve various problems, organizational skills and leadership qualities. All these indicators are improving. One of the goals of professional teacher training is the development of human resources and training of personnel in educational institutions.

A professional retraining course is professional didactic training and pedagogical skills of a specialist, not only the required level of professional knowledge, but also psychological preparation, self-management and the educational process, professional, spiritual, physical and personal abilities. skills, such as the ability to correctly orient the problem being solved in a situation.

Didactic competence combines professional theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and professionally important personal qualities. That is, so that the teacher has theoretical knowledge in the subjects necessary for his professional activity; a practical component that allows you to analyze a specific professional situation, solve the problem most effectively, important practical skills in the course of professional activity, a high professional attitude; the professional and personal component determines the professional and moral position of the teacher.

Since ancient times, scientists have emphasized the need to educate everyone, and success in this is the basis of all human life. A high educational environment in a school can be seen as an increase in human resources and efficiency. The effectiveness of any organization directly depends on how well its employees are trained. The concept of traditional education only conveys traditional cultural heritage. Changes will be driven by the different needs of a growing population. In the modern era, education cannot simply be a mediator between time and space. The current and future needs of the world we know, which people use at different stages of their lives, are associated with the living environment and educational processes [14].

The theoretical foundations of professional retraining of teachers are of great importance. In this regard, there are many ideas and approaches. If education is considered as a factor in the process of continuous retraining of teachers in terms of efforts to improve professional skills, then education will be effective.

The content of professional retraining and advanced training of teaching staff is that teachers have the opportunity to change their actions based on reading and learning, but this is achievable and desirable only if their work activity changes with age. That's when real change happens.

The goal of teacher professional development must be consistent with the goals of the program. Increasing knowledge and skills is a fundamental tool in solving today's complex and changing problems. Improving the quality of education depends on improving the professional potential of teachers. Students must have special knowledge and professional skills. Therefore,

this education is fully supported. Professional retraining of personnel is one of the most important management tasks.

As one of the important scientific results of the study, the possibilities for developing didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining were improved based on the development of independent creative activity, the effective use of best practices, the formation of action programs and the stable provision of dynamics for monitoring the results of repeated test assessments and the acquisition of new knowledge.

It should be noted that professional training is psychological, psychophysiological, physical and scientific-theoretical and practical training of the future specialist [5].

As one of the important scientific results of the study, the issues of effective use of best practices in increasing the didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining based on the effective use of best practices were considered. Effective use of best practices in education includes all aspects related to the implementation of best teaching practices. Effective use of best practices in education allows you to direct it in the right direction.

In the process of professional retraining, we consider the process of developing students' didactic competence as a system. A system is a set of elements and interconnected components to achieve the intended results of work [15].

System development. A set of activities, methods, effective use of best practices and improvement of the classical systems model [15]. In the process of professional retraining, the system of the process of developing students' didactic competence is aimed at recognizing problems, understanding and analyzing difficulties, identifying and assessing the requirements necessary to make appropriate decisions, as well as evaluating the chosen solutions and work results.

It must be emphasized that the role of teacher training courses is seen as a very important area in developed and developing countries. Thus, teacher education, including postgraduate education, is important in the national interest (including the preservation of vital elements) [13].

Educational needs assessment. The identification of needs, as well as the need to assess potential, should lead to the reduction or elimination of difficulties [17]. In this study, assessment is one of the main elements of teacher preparation.

It can be argued that teachers have a say in every change in retraining, meaning that teachers have a major impact on owners' academic performance, motivation, independence and confidence.

Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions in the system of personnel retraining, improve the quality of teaching, radically update the educational methodology and technology of the educational process, improve modern educational and methodological support of the educational process, use best practices in the development and use of them is one of the important mechanisms for organizing adult education.

Also, as one of the important scientific results of the study, the possibilities for developing didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining have been improved based on the formation of action programs and the results of repeated test assessments and monitoring of new dynamics of knowledge acquisition (variable [4]).

The purpose of developing action programs is:

updating the content of continuous professional development courses based on a modular approach based on student action programs;

a combination of teaching activities and advanced training based on student activity programs - a broad organization of their professional development directly on the basis of schools; updating course content based on student action programs.

Students' action programs are an individual trajectory of professional development, developed taking into account their professional needs and aimed at self-development.

Students' physical exercise programs are recommended to consist of the following components:

topics and questions for self-reflection that will help achieve the desired educational outcomes;

a list of relevant literature for independent study or use in classes;

manuals, examples of successful practice, training materials;

tasks for self-development;

time standards.

Student activity programs are implemented through an individual professional development program.

Student action programs are an individual trajectory of professional development, developed taking into account their professional needs and aimed at self-development. Student action programs are aimed at achieving the following results:

- preparation for the profession, teaching and organization of the educational environment;
- preparation for proper planning and design of teaching activities;
- self-government and self-expression.

To create activity programs for trainees, it is recommended to follow these steps:

1. Selection of goals.
2. Make a list of tasks (things you want to learn or have).
3. Determine the resources needed to achieve the goal and plan how to obtain them.

The dissertation improves the possibilities for developing didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining based on the results of repeated test assessments and stable provision of dynamics for monitoring the acquisition of new knowledge;

Assessing the quality of education, its monitoring, and continuous improvement of indicators are today considered one of the most important areas and is the main task in ensuring the required level of quality of education.

Sh. Kurbanov, E. Seitkhalilov [6] stated that the process will be effective if various methods and means of assessment are used in education.

M. Akhmedov [2] stated that without assessment it is impossible to effectively manage the quality of the educational process and the entire educational system.

Based on this, the possibilities for developing the didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining have been improved based on the results of repeated test assessments and the stable provision of dynamics for monitoring the assimilation of new knowledge.

According to G. Koons [18], S. Donnell [18], assessment is the formation and application of standards and norms of activity. Thus, based on the results of repeated test assessment, the possibilities for developing the didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining are improved.

Monitoring the quality of the education system was studied by S.T. Turgunov [8], M.A. Yuldashev[10].

According to modern approaches to management, quality assurance is carried out in the following sequence: setting goals, planning, choosing methods and tools, monitoring and evaluation, analysis and correction [2].

R. Juraev[3] “monitoring is information designed to provide the management of the educational system with information that allows making informed conclusions about the educational system or its individual elements, assessing and analyzing its condition at any time of collection, processing, storage and distribution” [3] .

Sh. Kurbanov, E. Seitkhalilov [8] stated that monitoring the quality of education is a complex system aimed at monitoring the state and changes in the quality of education, its assessment and forecasting [8].

Monitoring in the field of education is constant monitoring of the educational process and its management [7].

By assessment we mean comparing knowledge, skills and qualifications with benchmarks (indicators, templates, scales) specified in the curriculum. The assessment refers to the numerical value of the assessment in the form of points. Supervision (in the educational process) means the process of determining, measuring and assessing the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of the student. Detection and measurement is called verification [9].

In the process of professional retraining, attention was paid to the constant monitoring of the educational process and its management, while the opportunities for developing the didactic competence of students were improved, the dynamics of monitoring the results of repeated test assessments and the acquisition of new knowledge were maintained.

Monitoring is considered as the most important, relatively independent section in the field of management in the theory of social management, and the results of teaching activities are identified and assessed within the framework of educational monitoring. Monitoring is a process of comprehensive observation, analysis, correction and forecasting of the state and dynamics of the entire system [9].

It should be noted that monitoring means constant monitoring. This is done based on the results of the re-test assessment.

Therefore, the development of didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining is manifested in the fact that in the course of work they set a goal for themselves, set tasks in accordance with it, select and design technologies for their work, and the goal and result correspond. Personal and professional needs for self-development, motivation and the definition of goals based on them are inextricably linked with the process of achieving the goal.

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